

Sign Language Users in Estonia: Language Demography Survey

Péter Zalán ROMANEK, Christian RATHMANN
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EVKUR

Eesti viipekeele uurimisrühm

HARIDUS- JA
TEADUSMINISTEERIUM

projekti toetab

Contextualization

Research questions

Methodology

Key Findings

Discussion

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Research in Language Demography

Language Demography (Turner, 2020; Moreno-Fernández, 2024)

Language Attitude and Choice (Krausneker 2015; Hill 2012, Kusters et al. 2022; Rowley & Cormier 2022)

Language Vitality (Webster, 2020; Webster, 2022)

Language Endangerment (Webster, 2019)

Sign Language Education (Mitchell, 2016)

Sign Language Interpreting (Cokely, 1981; Napier et al., 2021)

Language Planning and Policy (Reagan, 2022)

Snapshot

Estonia

- Laiapea et al. (2002)
- Toom & Trükkmann (2005)
- Statistikaamet (2011; 2022)

Issues:

- Categorization: dual membership
- Divergent numbers

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(1) How do age, gender, hearing status, and regional context influence patterns of sign language use and transmission within Estonian Deaf communities?

(2) How do early sign language acquisition experiences vary across demographic groups, and how are they associated with educational outcomes?

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2. Data Collection and Analysis Design

1. Design, Pretest and Translation

- > Questionnaire-based survey
- > Estonian SL and written Estonian

2. Data Collection

- > Online and on-site formats.

3. Quantitative Analysis

- > Descriptive statistics and correlation analysis

Video esitamine

(11-b) Ma tunnen end mugavalt, kui väljendan end suuliselt eesti keeles

1	2	3	4	5	ei oska öelda	ei soovi vastata

Järgmine →

- (12-c) kuulja
- (12-d) erivajadusega isik
- (12-e) CODA (Child of Deaf Adult, eestis: kurdi vanema kuulja laps)

Muu

(palun täpsusta)

Järgmine →

(12.) Kellega ja kui sageli sa viipekeeles suhtled?

Palun valige iga isiku puhul kõige sobivam vastus.

1 - Ei viiple. 2 - Viiplen harva. 3 - Viiplen aeg-ajalt. 4 - Viiplen sageli.

	1	2	3	4
12-a) ema	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
12-b) isa	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
12-c) emapoolne vanaema	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Survey content overview (N=150)

- 32 questions on demographic data questions
- 30 questions on attitude and choice
- 5 questions on language vitality
- 2 questions on mental health
- 4 questions on language service

Data collection sites

Tallinn

Narva

Tartu

Võru

Kuressaare

N = 150

Sandra Laurimaa

10. Dezember 2024 · 🌐

Hea viipekeelne kogukond!

Vajan väga teie abi! Kuidas? Kohe kirjutan ja viiplen täpsemalt 🙏👉

Minu nimi on Sandra Laurimaa. Alates selle aasta veebruarist olen ma Tallinna Ülikooli doktorant-nooremteadur ja eesti viipekeele uurimisrühma (EVKUR) liige.

Novembris sai valmis EVKURi ühe esimese uurimusega seotud veebiküsitlus, mille teemaks on keeledemograafia ja keele suhtumine eesti viipekeelse kogukonnas.

Mehr anzeigen— 🌹 hoffnungsvoll mit Jari Pärigma und Romanek Péter Zalán.

👍👍👍 Du, Hrestana Berezjuk, Bella Kurg und 68 weitere Personen

7 Kommentare

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Basic Descriptive Statistics

Geographical distribution (N=150)

Distribution of age ($N=150$)

Gender (N=150)

■ woman ■ man ■ does not want to answer

Hearing status (N=150)

■ Deaf ■ hard-of-hearing ■ hearing

**Estonian Sign Language as a National Sign
Language in Multilingual Context**

Hearing status and primary language (N=150)

Hearing status and primary language (N=150)

Hearing status and EVK as primary language (N=84)

Patterns of Sign Language Acquisition

Onset of Deafness and Age of Sign Language Acquisition (N=150)

Age of Sign Language Acquisition among Deaf Respondents (N=45)

Sign Language Visibility

Aggregated heatmap showing respondents' perceptions of sign language visibility (N=150)

Educational Challenges

Distribution of highest education level among respondents who acquired Sign Language before age 12 (N=81)

Age of Sign Language acquisition among Deaf and hard-of-hearing respondents with highest education level (N=104)

Five Key Results

(1) Sign Languages in Estonia

(2) Everyday Multilingual Practices

(3) Early Sign Language Acquisition in Sign Language Environments

(4) Sign Language Use and Visibility in Sign Language Environments

(5) Sign Language Acquisition and Educational Outcomes

Discussion: Six Key Points I.

1. Language demography as a methodological innovation and its challenges in small Deaf communities
2. Collaboration with national Deaf associations, Deaf clubs, and other Deaf stakeholders
3. Importance of exposure to Sign Language environments

Discussion: Six Key Points II.

4. Access to Sign Language use and environments
5. Language demography as a toolkit for designing Sign Language-related services (acquisition, education, interpreting)
6. Relevance for Sign Language planning and policy development

Acknowledgment

<https://www.facebook.com/photo/?fbid=1179045070932438&set=pcb.1179045860932359>

Aitäh!